

INTERNET USE, SELF-EFFICACY AND PERCEIVED STRESS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

*In the process of empowering oneself holistically, one cannot undermine the role of self-efficacy. Further, coping with everyday hassles effectively and most importantly our perception of stress plays a very crucial role in grooming ourselves adequately. Considering the importance of both in this techno-friendly world, the present study was conducted to understand internet use, Problematic internet use. In addition, it also looked into self-efficacy and Perceived stress among Undergraduate students in Bhubaneswar and Cuttack. The study adopted Internet Addiction Test (Kimberly young,1998), General Self-efficacy Scale (Schwarzer, et.al;1995) and Perceived Stress Scale (PSS, Sheldon Cohen,1988) on 104 participant undergraduate students (48 male ,56 female). The study revealed a positive correlation ($r = .590$) between internet use and perceived stress among undergraduate students. Further, it was revealed that gender has significant effect on internet use ($t = 1.99, p < .01^{**}$), self-efficacy ($t = -2.97, p < .02^{**}$) and perceived stress ($t = 1.13, p < .03^{**}$). Hence, the study is expected to be helpful in addressing various mental health issues and will support the future research.*

Keywords: *Internet use, Problematic internet use, Self-efficacy, Perceived Stress, Technology*

Introduction

Humans being, the supreme creature on earth embedded with individual uniqueness. This uniqueness not only speaks about uniqueness in thoughts and ideas but uniqueness in perception. Perception is no less that a boon to the human kind. It is subjective in nature and

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makes individual's personality distinct. Doesn't matter how the world really is, it will be visible how you want to look at it. The world will look dull and gloomy, if your perception towards the world is depressing. Similarly, it will look promising with the brighter view. Therefore, it is important to understand perception towards stress. World health organization (WHO) stated health as a complete balance between physical, mental and social wellbeing which can't be achieved just nullifying the diseases. So, being healthy is not just having proper diet and exercise, it also indicated through individual's emotional stability, coping mechanism towards stress. Mental health is equally responsible factor as biological health or social environment contributing towards individual's quality of life.

In today's world the definition of stress also varies from person to person. Some finds daily life events stressful some manage it smoothly but difficult manage work life stress or relationship. Definition of stress is pretty subjective to its arousing source. It also depends on how a person sees himself/herself capable of dealing with the assigned task or world. The perception of one's ability is referred as individual's self-efficacy. Self-efficacy can contribute individual's wellbeing. Self-efficacy "refers to beliefs in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments" (Bandura, 1997). Its an overall perception of an individual on his/her abilities. It can otherwise define as a self-belief on one's own potentials. Hence, it is correct to assume, higher the self-efficacy, the more optimistic views an individual have towards self.

Advancement of technology influenced people's lifestyle to a large extent. Also, Use of Internet has become easily accessible to people. The world of today is the world of technology and technological advancements. It not only contributed to individual's life style. But it made easier to the entire world get connected on fingertip. Significant internet based technological upgradation that helps individual in areas like learning, education, entertainment, just to name a few. Use of Internet has become as easy and accessible as nursery rhymes to people. As every coin has both the sides, hence it is expected that use of technology and internet-based exploration must also include the same.

Review of literature

Kumar.M and Mondol.A(2018) found in their research work that individuals with high internet use diagnosed with depression and anxiety. Further, internet addiction also found associated with obsessive compulsive disorder and interpersonal sensitivity.

Similarly, a study by Hassan.T, et.al;(2020) on 'prevalence & associated factors of internet addiction among young adults (19-35yrs) in Bangladesh'. The findings of the study confirmed

high rate of internet addiction in younger participants. Also shown a disconnected family, long distance stay from family were considered important mental health indicators.

Yang's study (2020) on middle school students struck out a strong negative relationship between self-efficacy and internet addiction, while assessing their effects on internet addiction.

Berte et al. (2021) study surveyed Palestinian college students, highlighted a negative link identified between Problematic internet use and self-efficacy.

Gong.Z, et.al;(2021) in their study on college students found a significant association between Perceived stress and internet addiction. Also, they noted Procrastination has important role in mediating between Perceived stress and internet addiction.

Research Objectives

- To study the relationship between perceived stress and internet use among undergraduate students.
- To look into the relationship between self-efficacy and internet use among undergraduate students.
- To assess the relationship between perceived stress and self-efficacy among undergraduate students.
- To examine gender difference in relation to internet use among undergraduates.
- To examine gender difference in relation to self-efficacy among undergraduate students.
- To examine gender difference in relation to perceived stress among undergraduate students.

Hypotheses

It is hypothesized that

- There will be relationship exist among internet use, self-efficacy and perceived stress.
- Gender difference in internet use, self-efficacy and Perceived stress will be found.

Method of Study

Sample

The sample of study consists of 104 youth undergraduate students (48 male and 56 female) from various educational institutions of Bhubaneswar and cuttack. The age of the participants ranges between 18-22yrs.

Tools:

The current study used the following tools for collecting data from the students

- Informed consent

- Socio demographic sheet
- Internet Addiction Test by Kimberly young (1998)
- General Self efficacy Scale (Schwarzer, et.al;1995)
- Perceived Stress Scale (Sheldon Cohen et.al;1988)

Design

The study used between subject design. The independent variables for the study were Gender (male and female). The dependent variables are internet use, Self-efficacy and perceived stress.

Procedure:

All participants were from various educational institute of Cuttack and Bhubaneswar. The investigator personally met all the one hundred four (104) participants and consent from all participants were taken. The investigator individually interacted with the participants and briefly explained about the objective and process of the study to the participants.

After the rapport established successfully, each participant was instructed to fill up the internet addiction test (IAT) with his/her genuine response. Further, students were administered with generalized self –efficacy scale and Perceived stress scale individually in the same process.

Results

Considering the objective of research the relationship between Internet Use, Self-Efficacy and Perceived stress among undergraduate students were examined. The purpose also included assessed the role of gender on Internet Use, Self-Efficacy and Perceived stress. The below mentioned revealed about inter correlation matrix of internet use, self-efficacy and perceived stress among undergraduate students in table 1 and gender difference in internet use, self-efficacy and perceived stress among undergraduate students.

Table 1. Inter Correlation matrix of Internet Use, Self-Efficacy and Perceived Stress among undergraduate student

Variable	Internet Use	Self Efficacy	Perceived Stress
Internet Use	-	-.141	.590**
Self-Efficacy	-.141	-	.040
Perceived Stress	.590**	.040	-

Note: N=104. **p < .01

Table:-1 is displaying the inter correlation matrix of Internet use, Self-efficacy, Perceived Stress. Analysis of table has shown that a strong correlation ($p < .01$) between internet use and perceived stress was ($r = .590$). It indicated that as internet use among undergraduate students increased perceived stress also increased. And the study also revealed that there is no significant correlation exist between self – efficacy and internet use and self – efficacy and perceived stress.

Table:-2 Gender Difference on Internet Use, Self-Efficacy and Perceived stress among undergraduate students

Variables	Male		Female		T
	M	SD	M	SD	
Internet Use	48.42	20.47	41.25	16.41	1.99**
Self-Efficacy	26.77	6.59	30.30	5.52	-2.97**
Perceived Stress	23.90	4.68	21.63	6.10	1.13**

Note. N = 104. Higher scores indicate a greater magnitude of each variable. All analyses are two- tailed. * *p <.01 Table :- 2 is describing Gender difference in the internet use, self-efficacy and perceived stress among undergraduate students. The means, standard deviations and ‘t’ value of two groups of participants (males and females) for internet use, self-efficacy and

perceived stress are presented in Table 2. Analysis of the data using the independent t-test for equal variances indicated that males showed significantly higher internet use ($t=1.99$, $p<.01$) than females. Whereas, females showed higher self-efficacy ($t = -2.97$, $p<.01$) than males. In perceived stress, males also exhibited significantly higher score ($t = 1.13$, $p<.01$) than females.

Conclusion

The study found a positive link ($r = .590$) between perceived stress and internet use among undergraduate students. In simple terms, the more students used the internet, the more stressed they felt. This aligns with a study by Ishmail (2023) on adolescents in South Arabia, which showed that high internet usage increases stress, anxiety, and depression.

The study also revealed that gender significantly impacts internet use ($t = 1.99$, $p < .01^{**}$). Male students used the internet more than female students on average and also reported higher levels of perceived stress. This supports the hypothesis that increased internet use leads to higher stress levels.

Previous studies also back these findings. Research shows that men tend to spend more time online, engage more with technology, and focus on digital learning compared to women (Cooper, 2006; Correa, 2010; Fallows, 2005; Livingstone & Helsper, 2007; Losh, 2004; Pinkard, 2005; Wilson, Wallin, & Reiser, 2003).

Female students are less involved in internet-based activities, even when people have the freedom to pursue their interests, societal structures can shape their behaviour and priorities. This could be because cultural and psychological factors may discourage some groups, like women, from using technology, even when they have access (Terry & Gomez, 2010).

Interestingly, the study found that female students showed higher self-efficacy than male students (Ifdil, 2016). This might be due to socialization processes that expose women to more social support, which helps build their confidence in handling challenges (Tiffere, 2020).

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